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Women Empowerment's Mechanism, Case Study Tunisia

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ABSTRACT

The woman is the family's backbone. She brings life to the world and contributes to the education of future generations. In ancient times, the woman, in the Arab world, had a narrow role based on gender and physical abilities. The woman has to carry out Household Chores which has included resources management, cleaning, washing, and cooking, to provide a comfortable and healthy environment for her children and husband.

Meanwhile, to provide for his family's needs, the man must work a job that generally requires physical skills.

As societies have evolved, the Women's roles have gradually changed. Today's Women are directly involved in the socio-economic cycle and contribute to their country's development. Furthermore, several women have influenced societies, held high positions, and demonstrated strong leadership and management abilities.

In response to the needs of the times, leaders and decision-makers have seized the opportunity to change history. However, the path of modernizing societies and liberating women was challenging. Arab Governments needed to conciliate between the cultural Islamic tradition and the modern civic social concepts. Furthermore, they were required to establish new civic values, cultivate a particular social mindset based on justice and fairness, implement the necessary measures, and perform changes. In this context, we attempt to examine the situation of women in Tunisia and analyze the mechanisms that contributed to women's liberation following independence.

Keywords

Women, Tunisia-Women's Liberation, Empowerment, Women's Rights, Education, Society, Policies, Economy, Society-Nation, State Building.

Empowerment Definition:

Empowerment has different definitions but they are sharing common elements resumed in process, communities, active participation, critical reflection, awareness and understanding of the influence of political power and economic structures and interests, and involve access to and control over important decisions and resources. There's another definition of empowerment that didn't mention the creation of a climate of mutual respect and caring that includes the practice of empowerment of political and civic leaders. Empowerment can be a process, life, and outlook-changing outcome for individuals, organizations, and communities. [1]

At the International Conference on "People's Empowerment and Development", in Dhaka, Bangladesh, on 5 August 2012, the UN Former Secretary-General Mr. Ban Ki-moon stated that Empowerment is a key means to achieving sustainable development and other vital goals. It ensures that people have the opportunities they need to live better lives in dignity and security. He also praised the establishment of UN Women and the effort to empower the world's women and achieve gender equality. [2]

Introduction:

Before its independence in 1956, Tunisia was ruled by France. At that time, Tunisian society had no defined structure and it was built on a masculine foundation, with no room for women to participate directly in social life. Since the reign of the Ottomans, the society had primarily adopted cultural-religious traditions and Islamic legislation (*sharia*) as a way of life. Moreover, the country had a tribal structure, but the French protectorate encouraged nomadic tribes' integration into national life. [3] Although, the general situation, advocates for women's freedom and rights, such as "Taher Haddad," have emerged. The Tunisian reformer is well known for his work "Our Woman in Sharia and Society," published in 1930. Due to the sensitivity of the discussed subject, he was regarded as a courageous activist. The work reflected both his intellectual foresight and practical reform of Tunisian women's status. [4]

Following the country's independence, Tunisia's new government began the nation-state-building process, which required the participation of all elements of society. The government has implemented a population policy, disbanded tribal organizations, modernized and structured society, and integrated women into social life.

Haddad and women's Liberation Aspect:

Before independence, the Tunisian society used the legislation as a basic reference. Taher Haddad's work "Our Woman in Sharia and Society" has criticized masculine social dominance and clarified several points

regarding legislation and society. His work was divided into two sections: legislative and social. The legislative section has addressed the issue of a woman's status in Islam and her given rights, which at that time, are no longer fully exercised.

The author explained that Islamic legislation has granted women rights to ensure complete equality and fairness between men and women. However, due to historical circumstances, Muslim women's rights have gradually declined and been ignored.

In the social section, the reformer has pointed out several practical ideas for woman's education such as mind and spirit formation and urged her integration into society. [5]

Tahar Haddad's vision is regarded as a historical precedent for Tunisian women's liberation. He emphasized the related issues of women's rights. In addition to criticism, he introduced practical methods for empowering society through women's education. His work and ideas have sparked heated debates among Tunisians and the Arab world. Furthermore, it has laid the foundation for future reforms in the field.

Major Policies Shaping the New Women's Status in Tunisia:

The Constitution 1956:

Tunisia's new women's status has been shaped by several policies. The constitution of 1956 stated that the republican regime constitutes the most effective way of protecting the family and ensuring the citizens' right to work, health care, and education. Article six stated that "all citizens have equal rights and responsibilities and are equal before the law." [6]

In the nation-state building process, the new republican system didn't exclude any member of society. It's encouraging the participation of all the members, regardless of religion and gender. The government's mission was to establish a modern society in which all of its members are united and coexist in harmony. Since July 25, 1957, Tunisia has become a republican country that emphasizes the ideals of rule of law, human dignity, civic values, justice, equality, and personal development.

Personal Status Code:

One of the most brilliant achievements in Bourguiba's presidency term is the "Personal Status Code". It has shaped Tunisian society and built the foundation of Tunisian civism and modernity.

On August 13, 1956, the government has issued a personal status code which marked the beginning of the Tunisian people's journey to modern citizenship in terms of rights and responsibilities. The creation of The

Personal Status Code remains a major key in nation-building. The code contains civic Tunisian laws that organized the family, established equality between women and men, and ensured children and woman's rights. It contains 213 articles that regulated laws regarding marriage, spousal rights and obligations, spousal disputes, filiation, dissolution of marriage, legal representation and guardianship, and Inheritance. The Personal status code notably abolished polygamy, created a judicial procedure for divorce, and required marriage to be performed only in the event of the mutual consent of both parties. [7]

The new regulations have guaranteed the rights of women, organized the family, and created a civilized modern society ready to contribute to the country's development. Since then, the 13 of august become Tunisian women's day celebrating the social, economic, cultural, and political achievements of women.

Population Policy:

In 1960, the Tunisian government has made the Approval of family planning and Birth control program. The state started awareness campaigns regarding the issue. Furthermore, it has established many care centers and hospitals. As result, Tunisia witnessed an improvement in infant health, and the life expectancy has jumped from 42 years in 1960 to 65 years in 1985. [8]

Family planning and birth control programs benefit society as well as women. It was necessary to create a balance between population growth and economic and social needs. The role of Tunisian women has greatly expanded, resulting in new missions and challenges. Their contribution to education and the labor force exemplifies their integration into society.

Empowering the Tunisian Women Via Education:

Tunisian education was a pillar in the nation-state building process. After the independence, the government has implemented several reforms that directly contributed to the development of the society and the economy as well.

The reform of 1958 has defined the structure of the system of education into primary secondary and high education. The system of education became modernized and unified. Indeed, the remarkable policies of the "Education Act" have shaped education and accomplished justice and equality between genders.

In 1958, the Tunisian government issued "The Education Act". Chapter two indicates that the state provides education to all children starting at six years old. Moreover, in chapter three, the Tunisian government has approved free and compulsory education at all levels. Meanwhile, Chapter Seven stipulates that Primary education is unified and nationalized, and its essential goal is to empower the child with basic knowledge in the fields of language and arithmetic, aiming at emphasizing his capabilities, achieving compatibility

between him and his environment, and revealing his talents that will guarantee guidance in the following stages of his learning.[9]

The “Education Act” has created equality and justice between the genders. It’s giving equal opportunities especially since girls’ education was a fundamental issue during colonial times. Therefore “the doors to education became open to all children, starting from the age of six. [10]

As result, in the scholar year of 1958/59, primary education has in total of 320,362 enrolled students including 102,227 girls which represented 31, 9% of the total number. In 1969/70’s scholar year, the female enrollment has increased to 38.7%. [11]

In the scholar year of 1957/58, the Secondary education has only 21,486 enrolled students including 18,794 boys and 2,692 girls. In 1969/70 there were 163,353 enrolled students including 119,604 boys and 43,749 girls. The rate of female presence has increased from 12.5% in 1957/58 to 26.8% in 1969/70. [12]

In Higher education, concerning the scholar year of 1956/57, ten universities in total had 639 students including 85 females, meanwhile, in 1970/71, the high education witnessed an increase in the enrollment rate to reach 7445 students including 2005 females, they are all dispensed in twelve different universities.[13]

Concerning the educational bodies, in 1970 secondary education had 4,044 Tunisian teachers, including 700 women in duties. Tunisian female teachers represent only 17.3% and they mainly occupied the positions of assistant professors or assistant teachers. [14]

It should be mentioned that after the independence during Bourguiba’s presidency term, the Tunisian government has started the nation-state building process and gradually allocated the necessary resources to achieve targets regarding the infrastructure such as universities and schools, hospitals, telecommunication, transport, and public services. And this should be taken into consideration regarding the results of the education system and the student enrollment rates specifically in higher education. However, we can’t neglect the gap of genders between males and females in Tunisian education.

In the following years, the Tunisian government strengthened the education system. In 1991, the leaders supported the educational policies, applied new reforms, and integrated basic education. [15] By the year 2008, to internationalize education, the authorities started the deployment of the Bologna System (Licenses-Master Degree - Doctorate). [16] Since 1956, all the education reforms had a great educational and social impact and we can notice satisfying results.

Regarding basic education, in the population of 10-year-olds and over, from the year 1994 to 1999 the girls’ illiteracy rate has decreased from 42.3% to 32.5, meanwhile for the same period concerning the population aged between 10 and 29 the girl’s illiteracy rate has decreased from 19.7 to 9.4% [17]

Concerning the secondary education national exam, the girl's Baccalaureate success rates have increased from 49.5% in 1997 to 72.9% in 2002, against 43.3% and 68.7% respectively for the boys. [18] In higher education, the female presence has progressed and become overrepresented in universities. There has been a significant increase in the number of enrolled female students in universities, from 19.4% in 1965/66 to 59.5% in 2008/09. [19] In 2003, the female presence in the vocational training sector has represented 36% of the workforce of the Tunisian Agency for Vocational Training, against 27% in 1996. In the educational bodies, in the year 2000, Women have represented 38% of higher education teaching staff and 35% of university researchers. [20]

The Tunisian government's strategy of integrating women into society has been successful, and it has gradually built a nation that shares human and civic values. Women's liberation has brought benefits and fueled the country's development. Education has a significant impact on women's integration into society and their socio-economic contribution.

Women's Achievements:

Tunisian women achieved many goals. In 1978/79 an elite of educated women such as executives, teachers, journalists, lawyers, and students have created the "Club Tahar Haddad". This club is committed to the studies of women's status in Tunisia and addresses the major encountered issues. The club members criticized the women's limited political participation and prompted demands for further rights. [21]

As result, Tunisian women became active and productive in the political scene, the first Tunisian woman minister, Fathia Mazali, took office in 1983. Concerning the legislative power, the rate of female deputies rose to 11.5% in 1999 compared to 7.4% in 1994. [22]

In 1985, the "Nissa Group" created a bi-monthly journal to address women's issues. It has various objectives such as the defense of the Personal status code, encouragement of women's political participation, and highlighting the role of women in society. Between the years 1985 and 1987, the group has discussed and exposed several issues. [23]

In the year 2004, The Tunisian Parliament has 21 women out of a total of 182 deputies. The positions of second vice-president of the Chamber of Deputies and the chairman of a committee are held by women. Women occupy 13.6% of the total number of members of government. They are in charge of several departments such as the Ministry of Affairs of the Women, Family, and Childhood, and State Secretariats for Housing, Establishments Hospitals, Social Promotion, Foreign Affairs, and Childhood. Moreover, within the judiciary, women represent 25.7% of the body of the judiciary and 26% of the national workforce of lawyers. [24]

In addition, the state promoted the economic independence of women, encouraged the development of women via education, and female entrepreneurship, and strengthened the economic capacity and business networks of women.

The percentage of women with a functional job in the civil service rose from 15.15% in 2000 to 22.17% in 2003. Women's integration in economic life has steadily increased; their participation rate in the labor force has increased from 22.9% in 1994 to 25% in 2004. [25]

In 2004, the Tunisian female workforce represented 23.6% in the agricultural sector, 37.2% in industry, and 39.2% in the trade and services sector. Besides, the Tunisian government has implemented financial procedures offering loans to support women's economic projects. The rate of women beneficiaries of these loans has increased from 34.5% in 2001 to 37.4% in 2002 and 40.3% in 2003. In 2004 statistics shows that 15.7% of women are self-employed, while 67% are employees and apprentices. [26]

All these implemented measures have facilitated the integration of women in the economic sector and contributed to the decrease of the female unemployment rate. Statistics show that the female unemployment rate has decreased from 17.5% in 1994 to 15.15% in 2005. [27]

Conclusion:

The Tunisian government has allocated the necessary resources to create a climate that enables the participation of all the social components in the nation-state building. As result, it has created awareness and understanding among the Tunisian community and it has facilitated the implementation of the required mechanism to achieve the long-term goal of the liberation of women and accomplish their integration into society.

The republican system, the constitution, and the policies implemented in education and social life have modernized society and raised awareness among Tunisians, encouraging them to be active and united citizens in order to contribute to the country's development.

To comply with the current trends, the Tunisian march toward women's empowerment must take additional steps. Tunisia continues to experience regional disparities in rural areas, which have an impact on women's empowerment mechanisms such as education, access to health care, and employment.

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